

SOIL FERTILITY PROFILE IN THE CAPARAÓ CAPIXABA GEOGRAPHICAL INDICATION REGION UNDER ARABICA COFFEE CULTIVATION

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ABSTRACT: Coffee farming plays a crucial role in the socioeconomic development of Espírito Santo, contributing to job creation and, consequently, keeping people in rural areas, in addition to generating revenue from sales. Although it is well known that the genetic and productive potential of coffee crops exceeds current contents, the question arises: how to mitigate this discrepancy? Despite the technological resources available for coffee farming, the sector still faces significant obstacles to competitiveness, including rugged topography, low average productivity due to the introduction of less productive varieties, susceptibility to pests and diseases, and inadequate nutritional management, evidenced by the insufficient use of soil and foliar analyses by producers. Soil analysis is an important tool for assessing soil fertility and making accurate recommendations for soil amendments and fertilizers. Therefore, this study aimed to characterize the current fertility profile of soils cultivated with Arabica coffee in the Caparaó region of Espírito Santo state (Caparaó Capixaba). This study was carried out in the municipalities of Ibatiba, Ibitirama, Irupi, Iúna, Muniz Freire, and Guaçuí, within the Caparaó Capixaba geographical indication region. Composite soil samples (520) were collected from commercial units cultivated with Arabica coffee of different ages and in production stage. The samples were sent for chemical analysis aiming to determine macronutrient contents. From the results, the following conclusions were reached: i) soils sampled from the Caparaó Capixaba region are deficient in calcium and magnesium; ii) potassium and sulphur were found in high contents in soils of all municipalities; iii) and, that high contents of phosphorus were found in the soils of the municipalities of Caparaó Capixaba region.

KEYWORDS: Soil analysis. *Coffea arabica*. Soil Characterization.

PERFIL DA FERTILIDADE DOS SOLOS NA REGIÃO DA INDICAÇÃO GEOGRÁFICA CAPARAÓ CAPIXABA SOB CULTIVO DE CAFÉ ARÁBICA

RESUMO: A cafeicultura desempenha um papel crucial no desenvolvimento socioeconômico do Espírito Santo, contribuindo para geração de empregos e, conseqüentemente, para fixação do homem no meio rural, além da arrecadação de recursos provenientes da comercialização. Embora seja notório que o potencial genético e produtivo das lavouras supere os índices atuais,

surge a questão: como mitigar essa discrepância? Apesar do aparato tecnológico disponível para a cafeicultura, o setor ainda enfrenta obstáculos significativos à competitividade, dentre eles estão a topografia acidentada, a baixa produtividade média devido a introdução de variedades menos produtivas e susceptíveis a pragas e doenças e o manejo nutricional inadequado, evidenciado pelo uso insuficiente de análises de solo e foliar, pelos produtores. Uma ferramenta importante para avaliar a fertilidade do solo e fazer uma recomendação correta de corretivos e fertilizantes é a análise de solo. Com isso, este estudo teve como finalidade caracterizar o perfil da fertilidade atual dos solos cultivados com café arábica na região do Caparaó Capixaba. Esse estudo foi conduzido nos municípios de Ibatiba, Ibitirama, Irupi, Iúna, Muniz Freire e Guaçuí, região da indicação geográfica Caparaó Capixaba. Foram coletadas 520 amostras compostas de solos em unidades comerciais cultivadas com café arábica em diferentes idades e em produção. As amostras foram encaminhadas para serem analisadas para determinação dos teores de macronutrientes. A partir dos resultados das análises químicas dos solos amostrados, foram obtidas as seguintes conclusões: que os solos amostrados da região do Caparaó Capixaba são deficientes em cálcio e magnésio, que o Potássio e o enxofre foram encontrados em altos teores nos solos de todos os municípios e, por fim, que foram encontrados altos teores de fósforo nos solos dos municípios do Caparaó Capixaba.

PALAVRAS-CHAVE: Análise de Solo. *Coffea arabica*. Caracterização de Solos.

1 INTRODUCTION

Coffee farming in Brazil plays a crucial role in socioeconomic development. Within the agricultural sector, the activity stands out for its intensive absorption of labour and for keeping people in rural areas, in addition to generating jobs, tax revenue, and foreign exchange earnings (VOLSI *et al.*, 2019). This is the main agricultural activity in Espírito Santo state and is developed in almost all municipalities of the state, generating around 400,000 direct and indirect jobs, present in approximately 60,000 of the 90,000 agricultural properties in this Brazilian state. In this activity, around 73% of producers in Espírito Santo are family-based, involving 131,000 producing families, on properties averaging eight hectares (INCAPER, 2025). According to the third survey of the Brazilian coffee harvest by CONAB in 2025, Arabica coffee occupies approximately 121,000 hectares in the state, with a productivity of 26.8 bags of 60 kg per hectare (CONAB, 2025).

Although it is well known that the genetic and productive potential of coffee crops exceeds current contents (CONAB, 2025), the question arises: how to mitigate this discrepancy? Despite the technological resources available for coffee farming, the sector still faces significant obstacles to competitiveness, including rugged topography, low average productivity due to the introduction of less productive varieties, susceptibility to pests and diseases, and inadequate nutritional management, evidenced by the insufficient use of soil and foliar analyses by producers.

The soil fertility assessment is essential for coffee cultivation, both for regional development and to support the adoption of new technologies aimed at increasing productivity (PIRES *et al.*, 2003; GROTH *et al.*, 2013). Consequently, insufficient application of soil amendments and fertilizers will inevitably result in low productivity rates (GUARÇONI, 2017). Furthermore, the continuous use of land contributes to the degradation of natural resources, reducing their productive potential and interfering with their fertility (RODRIGUES *et al.*, 2016). Therefore, management must go beyond soil correction and fertilization, preserving the physical, chemical, and biological characteristics of the soil (RAMOS *et al.*, 2017). To this end,

management practices must be adopted in accordance with agricultural aptitudes, always taking into account the type and use of the soil, the relief, and the local climate (LEPSCH *et al.*, 1991).

Soil fertility analysis and performing recommendations for soil amendments and fertilizers through soil sampling are indispensable tools for accurately assessing soil fertility and supporting precise recommendations for amendments and fertilizers. However, for the sample to be representative of the area, the practice must follow procedures provided by research (CANTARUTTI *et al.*, 2007). The fertilization strategy should be designed to fully meet the plant's nutritional requirements, aiming for the expected production. This need is determined by the difference between the crop's total demand and the availability of nutrients already present in the soil, information obtained through soil analysis (MALAVOLTA, 1996).

According to the FAO - Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations, there is an undeniable need to increase food production. However, this increase must necessarily be based on the practice of increasingly sustainable agriculture (FAO, 2011). To this end, the efficient use of fertilizers is essential, based on the right source, dose, time, and place. Following these criteria, we ensure that the supply of nutrients is carried out according to the exact needs of the crops, resulting in greater productive efficiency and a significant reduction in field losses.

The soil fertility is a crucial factor for the sustainability of agricultural production, encompassing socioeconomic and environmental aspects. Therefore, it is important to identify appropriate and available technologies so that coffee farmers achieve desired results, benefiting society. To this end, we must focus on the use of tools such as soil sampling, the effective use of soil amendments and fertilizers, and the adoption of soil conservation practices. Such measures allow crops like coffee to express their full genetic potential. Thus, this study aimed to characterize the current fertility profile of soils cultivated with arabica coffee in the Caparaó Capixaba region of Espírito Santo state.

2 MATERIAL AND METHODS

This study was carried out in the municipalities of Ibatiba, Ibitirama, Irupi, Iúna, Muniz Freire and Guaçuí, in the Caparaó Capixaba geographical indication region (Figure 1), located in the Brazilian Atlantic Rain Forest biome. The soils where the samples were collected were classified according to Embrapa's classification, where two soil types were found in the study area: dystrophic red latosols and argisols (EMBRAPA, 2018).

Thus, 520 soil composite samples were collected from commercial units cultivated with Arabica coffee at different ages and in production. The soil samples were collected from the arable layer at a depth of 0–20 cm, following the composite sampling methodology. The composite sample consisted of combining twenty subsamples. The subsamples were collected from the projection of the coffee tree canopy, 60 days after the last fertilizer application. Right away, subsamples were then properly homogenized to obtain the composite sample and stored in plastic bags with appropriate identification (PREZOTTI *et al.*, 2007). The 520 samples were sent to the Labominas laboratory in Manhuaçu, Minas Gerais state, for analysis. At the laboratory, each sample was individually processed through air drying and sieving through a 2 mm mesh. After standardization, the samples were subjected to appropriate chemical analyses. The determination of macronutrient contents was carried out using the analytical methods described in Embrapa (EMBRAPA, 1997).

Figure 1: Studied municipalities of the Caparaó Capixaba region.

Based on the results of the chemical analyses of the sampled soils, the interpretation of the class tables for fertility contents for the nutrients Phosphorus (P), Potassium (K), Calcium (Ca), Magnesium (Mg), and Sulphur (S) (Table 1) was organized according to the evaluated chemical attributes. The soil fertility interpretation criterion adopted followed the standardization of the Fertilization and Liming Recommendation Manual for the state of Espírito Santo (PREZOTTI *et al.*, 2007).

The Soil texture was estimated based on remaining phosphorus (P-rem) for clayey and medium textures (Table 2), according to the fertilization and liming recommendation manual for Espírito Santo state (PREZOTTI *et al.*, 2007).

Table 1: Interpretation classes of fertility contents adopted for the Espírito Santo state, for phosphorus, potassium, calcium, magnesium and sulphur

Macronutrient	Unit	Classification			
		Low	Medium	High	
Phosphorus (P)	Clay texture	mg dm ⁻³	<5	5 - 10	>10
	Medium texture	mg dm ⁻³	<10	10 - 20	>20
	Sandy texture	mg dm ⁻³	< 20	20 - 30	>30
Potassium (K)	mg dm ⁻³	< 60	60 - 150	>150	
Calcium (Ca)	cmol _c dm ⁻³	<1,5	1,5 – 4,0	>4,0	
Magnesium (Mg)	cmol _c dm ⁻³	< 0,5	0,5 – 1,0	>1,0	
Sulphur (S)	mg dm ⁻³	< 5	5,0 – 10	>10	

Prezotti *et al.* (2007).

Table 2: Soil texture estimates as a function of remaining phosphorus - P-rem

P-rem (mg dm ⁻³)	Soil texture estimate
0 – 10	Clay
10 – 40	Medium
40 - 60	Sandy

Prezotti *et al.* (2007).

The average, maximum and minimum nutrient contents, coefficients of variation and frequencies of high, low, and medium contents were determined for each municipality. The similarity between municipalities as the studied variables was analyzed in the dendrogram constructed using the Average Euclidean Distance to measure the distance between two points

and the agglomerative hierarchical clustering method - UPGMA (Unweighted Pair Group Method with Arithmetic Mean). The main objective of this procedure is to maximize the homogeneity of municipalities within each group (clusters) and, simultaneously, maximize the heterogeneity between groups. The statistical analyses were performed using the R program (2025).

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Calcium content

Analyzing the calcium (Ca) contents, it was found that this element presented average contents of $2.67 \text{ cmol}_c \text{ dm}^{-3}$, varying from 0.30 to $7.20 \text{ cmol}_c \text{ dm}^{-3}$ in the municipality of Guaçuí. In Ibatiba, the Ca content in the soil ranged from 0.20 to $9.40 \text{ cmol}_c \text{ dm}^{-3}$, with an average of $2.69 \text{ cmol}_c \text{ dm}^{-3}$. According to the manual of recommendations for liming and fertilization for Espírito Santo (PREZOTTI *et al.*, 2007), a soil Ca content lower than $1.5 \text{ cmol}_c \text{ dm}^{-3}$ is considered low, from 1.5 to $4.0 \text{ cmol}_c \text{ dm}^{-3}$, medium, and higher than $4.0 \text{ cmol}_c \text{ dm}^{-3}$, high (Table 1). Thus, we can observe that in the municipality of Guaçuí, 24.14% of the samples showed low Ca contents, 13.79% high contents, and 62.07% medium contents. In the municipality of Ibatiba, 17.17% of the samples presented low Ca contents, 16.16% high contents, and 66.67% medium contents. In the municipality of Ibitirama, the content of this element in the soil varied from 0.20 to $6.90 \text{ cmol}_c \text{ dm}^{-3}$, with an average of $2.67 \text{ cmol}_c \text{ dm}^{-3}$, and 18.82% of the samples presented low Ca contents, 16.47% high contents, and 64.71% medium contents. In Irupi, the calcium content ranged from 0.80 to $7.70 \text{ cmol}_c \text{ dm}^{-3}$, with an average of $2.98 \text{ cmol}_c \text{ dm}^{-3}$. 10.67% of the samples showed low calcium contents, 21.33% high contents, and 68% medium contents. In Iúna, this content ranged from 0.60 to $9.90 \text{ cmol}_c \text{ dm}^{-3}$, with an average of $2.75 \text{ cmol}_c \text{ dm}^{-3}$. 21.65% of the samples showed low calcium contents, 57.73% medium contents, and 20.62% high contents. According to Muniz Freire, the Ca content in the soil ranged from 0.30 to $4.90 \text{ cmol}_c \text{ dm}^{-3}$, with an average of $2.32 \text{ cmol}_c \text{ dm}^{-3}$, with 25.97% of the samples showing low, 67.73% medium contents, and 6.49% showing high Ca content (Table 3).

Table 3: Statistical measurements of Calcium ($\text{cmol}_c \text{ dm}^{-3}$), for the municipalities of Guaçuí, Ibatiba, Ibitirama, Irupi, Iúna, and Muniz Freire

Statistical measurement	Municipalities					
	Guaçuí	Ibatiba	Ibitirama	Irupi	Iúna	Muniz freire
Medium content $\text{cmol}_c \text{ dm}^{-3}$	2.60	2.69	2.67	2.98	2.75	2.32
Maximum content $\text{cmol}_c \text{ dm}^{-3}$	7.20	9.40	6.90	7.70	9.90	4.90
Minimum content $\text{cmol}_c \text{ dm}^{-3}$	0.30	0.20	0.20	0.80	0.60	0.30
CV (%)	58.43	54.50	49.95	50.43	57.71	47.36
Frequency (%) high content	13.79	16.16	16.47	21.33	20.62	6.49
Frequency (%) low content	24.14	17.17	18.82	10.67	21.65	25.97
Frequency (%) Medium content	62.07	66.67	64.71	68.00	57.73	67.73

The observation of the combined results from the six municipalities in the Caparaó Capixaba region (Table 4) showed that the Ca content in the soil varied from 0.20 to 9.90 $\text{cmol}_c \text{dm}^{-3}$, with an average of 2.67 $\text{cmol}_c \text{dm}^{-3}$. The distribution of soil fertility for Ca showed that only 15.96% of the sampled soils had a high content of this element; more than 84% of these soils presented medium (64.23%) to low (19.81%) contents, requiring external supplementation. The most economical way to supply this element to the soil is through the application of quality limestone. In this context, this is important technology for plant growth and development and essential for them to express their genetic potential, with high productivity in more economical and profitable crops (NATALE *et al.*, 2012). However, the need for liming, which translates into the amount of limestone (PRNT 100%) to be applied to the soil (SOUZA, MIRANDA, OLIVEIRA, 2007), must be estimated responsibly (GUARÇONI, 2017). According to Dadalto and Fullin (2001), the low calcium contents found in the soils of the state of Espírito Santo are due to the parent material of these soils or to pedogenetic processes that favor losses by leaching.

Tabela 4: Statistical measurement of Cálcio (Ca), Magnésio (Mg), Potássio (K), Enxofre (S) e Fósforo (P) for the six studied municipalities of the Caparaó Capixaba region

Statistical measurement	Nutrient					
	Ca ($\text{cmol}_c \text{dm}^{-3}$)	Mg ($\text{cmol}_c \text{dm}^{-3}$)	K (mg dm^{-3})	S (mg dm^{-3})	P-clay soil (mg dm^{-3})	P-Medium texture (mg dm^{-3})
Medium content $\text{cmol}_c \text{dm}^{-3}$	2.67	0.70	149.82	23.00	29.78	68.11
Maximum content $\text{cmol}_c \text{dm}^{-3}$	9.90	2.80	798.00	59.00	245.80	606.40
Minimum content $\text{cmol}_c \text{dm}^{-3}$	0.20	0.10	30.00	6.00	1.90	1.30
CV (%)	53.96	53.80	65.83	53.43	131.96	111.60
Frequency (%) high content	15.96	14.81	39.04	91.92	64.52	66.92
Frequency (%) low content	19.81	26.92	12.88	0.00	16.13	16.92
Frequency (%) Medium content	64.23	58.27	48.08	8.08	19.35	16.16

3.2. Magnesium content

According to the liming and fertilization recommendation manual for Espírito Santo (PREZOTTI *et al.*, 2007), a soil content lower than 0.5 $\text{cmol}_c \text{dm}^{-3}$ is considered low, in the range of 0.5 to 1.0 $\text{cmol}_c \text{dm}^{-3}$, medium, and higher than 1.0 $\text{cmol}_c \text{dm}^{-3}$, high (Table 1). Thus, it was observed that Mg contents varied from 0.10 to 2.00 $\text{cmol}_c \text{dm}^{-3}$, with an average of 0.69 $\text{cmol}_c \text{dm}^{-3}$ in Guaçuí, and approximately 32.18% of the soils presented low Mg contents, 57.20% medium, and 10.34% high. In Ibatiba, the contents of this element varied from 0.10 to 2.20 $\text{cmol}_c \text{dm}^{-3}$, with an average of 0.67 $\text{cmol}_c \text{dm}^{-3}$. Approximately 25.25% of the soils in Ibatiba presented low Mg content, 61.62% medium, and only 13.13% high. Similar results were found in Ibitirama, where Mg content ranged from 0.10 to 1.50 $\text{cmol}_c \text{dm}^{-3}$, with an average of 0.70 $\text{cmol}_c \text{dm}^{-3}$, with 25.88% of the soils presenting low Mg content, 60.00% medium, and 14.12% high. Analysis of the results from the municipality of Irupi showed that Mg contents ranged from 0.20 to 1.90 $\text{cmol}_c \text{dm}^{-3}$, with an average of 0.8 $\text{cmol}_c \text{dm}^{-3}$. 13.33% of these soils presented low Mg contents, 60.00% medium contents, and 26.67% high contents, the latter being the highest frequency of high Mg contents found among the analyzed samples. Mg contents in the municipality of Iuna ranged from 0.20 to 2.80 $\text{cmol}_c \text{dm}^{-3}$, with an average of

0.71 $\text{cmol}_c \text{dm}^{-3}$. 31.96% of the samples from this municipality presented low Mg contents, 49.48% medium contents, and 18.56% high contents. Muniz Freire showed the lowest frequency of high Mg contents among the analyzed municipalities. The contents ranged from 0.10 to 1.40 $\text{cmol}_c \text{dm}^{-3}$ with an average of 0.62 $\text{cmol}_c \text{dm}^{-3}$, and 31.17% of the samples showed low Mg contents, 62.34% medium contents, and 6.49% high contents (Table 5).

Table 5: Statistical measurements of Magnesium, for the municipalities of Guaçuí, Ibatiba, Ibitirama, Irupi, Iúna, and Muniz Freire

Statistical measurement	Municipalitie					
	Guaçuí	Ibatiba	Ibitirama	Irupi	Iúna	Muniz freire
Medium content $\text{cmol}_c \text{dm}^{-3}$	0.69	0.67	0.70	0.80	0.71	0.62
Maximum content $\text{cmol}_c \text{dm}^{-3}$	2.00	2.20	1.50	1.90	2.80	1.40
Minimum content $\text{cmol}_c \text{dm}^{-3}$	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.20	0.20	0.10
CV (%)	57.20	52.83	46.92	51.31	61.83	45.51
Frequency (%) high content	10.34	13.13	14.12	26.67	18.56	6.49
Frequency (%) low content	32.18	25.25	25.88	13.33	31.96	31.17
Frequency (%) Medium content	57.47	61.62	60.00	60.00	49.48	62.34

The average of Mg contents in the Caparaó Capixaba region ranged from 0.10 to 2.80 $\text{cmol}_c \text{dm}^{-3}$, with an average of 0.70 $\text{cmol}_c \text{dm}^{-3}$, and more than 85% of these soils showed average (58.27%) and low (26.92%) Mg contents; only 14.81% showed Mg contents considered high (Table 4). The Mg result is similar to that obtained for the Ca element, confirming the need for supplementation of this nutrient through liming in this region, using material that provides this element in its composition. An important factor to be analyzed is the quality of the limestones applied to soils cultivated with coffee (RAMOS *et al.*, 2006; PREZOTTI *et al.*, 2007; ARAÚJO *et al.*, 2009).

The average Mg contents in the Caparaó Capixaba region ranged from 0.10 to 2.80 $\text{cmol}_c \text{dm}^{-3}$, with an average of 0.70 $\text{cmol}_c \text{dm}^{-3}$, and more than 85% of these soils showed average (58.27%) and low (26.92%) Mg contents; only 14.81% showed Mg contents considered high (Table 4). The Mg result is similar to that obtained for the Ca element, confirming the need for supplementation of this nutrient through liming in this region, using material that provides this element in its composition. An important factor to be analyzed is the quality of the limestones applied to soils cultivated with coffee (RAMOS *et al.*, 2006; PREZOTTI *et al.*, 2007; ARAÚJO *et al.*, 2009).

Analyzing Ca and Mg, we can observe in this study an improvement in the content of these nutrients in soils cultivated with coffee when compared to soils without anthropogenic alteration (PIRES *et al.*, 2003), and this improvement is related to liming and fertilization practices (EFFGEN *et al.*, 2008). According to these same authors, the calcium and magnesium contents in the soil are below what is considered adequate for coffee, indicating the need to use liming practices based on soil analysis, aiming to increase the availability of these nutrients and increase the efficiency of chemical fertilization.

3.3 Potassium content

According to the recommendation of Prezotti *et al.* (2007) for coffee plants, a K content in the soil of less than 60 mg dm⁻³ can be considered low; from 60 to 150 mg dm⁻³ medium, greater than 150 mg dm⁻³, high (Table 1).

The results in Table 6 show the statistical measurements for K for the municipalities of Guaçuí, Ibatiba, Ibitirama, Irupi, Iúna, and Muniz Freire. In the first, medium contents were found in 63.22% of the samples, followed by high (22.99%) and low (13.79%) contents, ranging from 35.0 to 429.0 mg dm⁻³ with an average of 122.33 mg dm⁻³. In Irupi, this average K content was found in 52.00% of the samples, high contents in 36.00%, and low contents in 12.00%, ranging from 30.00 to 404.00 mg dm⁻³ and an average of 151.79 mg dm⁻³. In Ibitirama, 44.71% of the samples showed average contents, followed by high contents (41.8%) and low contents (14.12%), ranging from 35.00 to 544.00 mg dm⁻³, with an average of 150.42 mg dm⁻³. In Muniz Freire, the frequency of average K contents was 48.05%, followed by high and low contents with 25.97%, values ranging from 31.00 to 251.00 mg dm⁻³, with an average of 112.12 mg dm⁻³. High potassium (K) contents were found in samples from the municipalities of Ibatiba and Iuna. In Ibatiba, high K contents were found in 49.49% of the samples, followed by medium (43.43%) and low (7.07%) contents, with contents ranging from 37.00 to 798.00 mg dm⁻³, with an average of 183 mg dm³. The high frequency of high contents of this element in the Iuna samples was 53.61%, 39.18% showed medium contents, and 7.22% showed low contents, ranging from 32.00 to 525.00 mg dm⁻³ and an average of 168.11 mg dm⁻³ (Table 6).

Table 6: Statistical measurements of Potassium, for the municipalities of Guaçuí, Ibatiba, Ibitirama, Irupi, Iúna, and Muniz Freire

Statistical measurement	Municipalitie					
	Guaçuí	Ibatiba	Ibitirama	Irupi	Iúna	Muniz freire
Medium content mg dm ⁻³	122.33	183.35	150.42	151.79	168.11	112.12
Maximum content mg dm ⁻³	429.00	798.00	544.00	404.00	525.00	251.00
Minimum content mg dm ⁻³	35.00	37.00	35.00	30.00	32.00	31.00
CV (%)	64.91	72.16	64.25	58.55	55.36	53.26
Frequency (%) high content	22.99	49.49	41.18	36.00	53.61	25.97
Frequency (%) low content	13.79	7.07	14.12	12.00	7.22	25.97
Frequency (%) Medium content	63.22	43.43	44.71	52.00	39.18	48.05

The combined data from the six municipalities in the Caparaó Capixaba region showed that K contents had a wide range of variation, from 30.00 to 798.00 mg dm⁻³, with an average of 149.82 mg dm⁻³. Average K contents were found in 48.08% of the samples from this region, 39.04% showed high contents, and 12.88% showed low contents (Table 4). Considering that the work was developed with soils cultivated with Arabica coffee in production, successive fertilizations in these crops with K promoted a residual effect that improves the chemical conditions of the soils (GOMES *et al.*, 2022). However, contents of K available in the soil can be rapidly reduced during periods of intense extraction of this nutrient by crop (LACERDA *et al.*, 2015).

In coffee cultivation, it is common to apply high doses of this nutrient without proper soil and foliar analysis, with adequate contents in the soil. This can lead to losses of K (GOMES

et al., 2022) or problems in the absorption of other nutrients such as Ca and Mg (XIE *et al.*, 2021; SENBAYRAM *et al.*, 2015) and increased production costs (PINTO *et al.*, 2017). The antagonistic effect of K on Mg is stronger than that of Mg on K in absorption and root transport within plants, indicating that the balanced use of K and Mg-based fertilizers is necessary to maintain high contents of Mg available to plants and mitigate K-induced deficiency of this element, especially in plant species with high K demand or in soils with high K availability (SENBAYRAM *et al.*, 2015; XIE *et al.*, 2021). These results demonstrated greater availability of K in the studied soils, which may result in lower production costs for this nutrient in fertilization programs (PIRES *et al.*, 2003). Even so, its supply to plants cannot be neglected, since continuous soil use without replenishment can lead to a deficiency of this nutrient (LANI, 1987). It also highlights the need for accurate soil analysis, which should be encouraged within productivity improvement and sustainability programs.

3.4 Sulphur content

Prezotti *et al.* (2007) showed that soil S content for coffee plants less than 5 mg dm⁻³ is considered low, from 5 to 10 mg dm⁻³, medium, and greater than 10 mg dm⁻³, high (Table 1).

High S contents predominated in samples from Ibatiba (96.97%), Ibatiba (96.97%), Ibitirama (94.14%), Irupi (96.00%), Iúna (93.81%), Muniz Freire (94.81%), and Guaçuí, which presented 75.86%, the lowest observed in this research (Table 7).

Sulphur contents ranged from 6.00 to 59.00 mg dm⁻³, with an average of 19.55 mg dm⁻³ in the municipality of Guaçuí. The frequency of this element in the analyzed samples showed that 100% presented medium (24.14%) to high (75.86%) contents. This behavior was repeated in all other municipalities. The highest S contents were found in Ibatiba, with a very similar result for sulphur, with contents ranging from 8.00 to 59.00 mg dm⁻³ and an average of 26.18 mg dm⁻³. 100% of the soils in Ibatiba have medium to high S contents, with 96.97% of the soils having high S and 3.03% having medium S. In the municipality of Ibitirama, S contents ranged from 8 to 57 mg dm⁻³, with an average of 25.48 mg dm⁻³. Presenting the same scenario as the other municipalities, 100% of the soils in Ibitirama have medium to high sulphur contents, with 94.12% of the soils having high sulphur content and 5.88% having medium sulphur content. For Irupi, sulphur contents ranged from 7 to 57 mg dm⁻³ with an average of 24.69 mg dm⁻³, and 100% of the soils have medium to high sulphur content, with 96.00% of the soils having high sulphur content and 4% having medium sulphur content. Analyzing the municipality of Iúna, sulphur contents ranged from 7.00 to 58.00 mg dm⁻³ with an average of 24.16 mg dm⁻³. The soils in Iúna had medium to high sulphur content (100%), with 93.81% of the soils having high sulphur content and 6.19% having medium sulphur content. Finally, in Muniz Freire, S followed the same trend, with contents ranging from 9.00 to 42.00 mg dm⁻³, with an average of 16.94 mg dm⁻³, and 100% of the soils with medium to high S contents, with 94.81% of the soils having high S contents and 5.19% having medium S contents.

Table 7: Statistical measurements of Sulphur for the municipalities of Guaçuí, Ibatiba, Ibitirama, Irupi, Iúna, and Muniz Freire

Statistical measurement	Município					
	Guaçuí	Ibatiba	Ibitirama	Irupi	Iúna	Muniz freire
Medium content mg dm ⁻³	19.55	26.18	25.48	24.69	24.16	16.94
Maximum content mg dm ⁻³	59.00	59.00	57.00	57.00	58.00	42.00
Minimum content mg dm ⁻³	6.00	8.00	8.00	7.00	7.00	9.00

CV (%)	67.42	52.24	49.22	47.60	48.79	34.33
Frequency (%) high content	75.86	96.97	94.12	96.00	93.81	94.81
Frequency (%) low content	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Frequency (%) Medium content	24.14	3.03	5.88	4.00	6.19	5.19

The joint observation of all municipalities in the studied region showed that 100% of the sampled soils presented S contents ranging from medium (8.08%) to high (91.92%) and that the average of the contents found in the 520 samples analyzed (23 mg dm⁻³) was more than double the critical content recommended for Arabica coffee (Table 4) (PREZOTTI *et al.*, 2007). In the Caparaó region, the use of simple and formulated fertilizers containing great amounts of S is common. Among these fertilizers, the main source is ammonium sulfate, which 24% S, making S available to the plant concomitantly with Nitrogen (CHAGAS *et al.*, 2019). Another source is the use of simple Superphosphate with 12% S, also widely used in the region (SILVÉRIO *et al.*, 2019).

This result raises concerns about an excess of this nutrient in the region, which may be causing toxicity and nutritional imbalance, inhibiting the absorption of other soil elements (LUCHETA; LAMBAIS, 2012). However, other sources of nitrogen and phosphorus can be used in coffee cultivation, such as urea and monoammonium phosphate (MAP), with the same efficiency (CHAGAS *et al.*, 2019; SILVÉRIO *et al.*, 2019).

3.5 Phosphorus content

The interpretation of phosphorus contents in the soil depends on the buffering capacity of this nutrient in the soil and its textural class (DADALTO; FULLIN, 2001). P recommendations for coffee cultivation in clay soils in Espírito Santo (PREZOTTI *et al.*, 2007) consider a soil content of less than 5 mg dm³ to be low, 5 to 10 mg dm⁻³ to be medium, and greater than 10 mg dm³ to be high. In medium-textured soils, a soil content of less than 10 mg dm³ is low, 10 to 20 mg dm³ to be medium, and greater than 20 mg dm⁻³ to be high; finally, in sandy soils, a soil content of less than 20 mg dm⁻³ is considered low, 20 to 30 mg dm⁻³ to be medium, and greater than 30 mg dm⁻³ to be high. In this study, we did not find any sandy-textured soil in the studied Caparaó region (Table 1).

3.5.1 Phosphorus in clay soils

It was found that the highest frequencies of high P content in clay soil samples came from the municipalities of Irupi (100%), Ibatiba (88.89%), Iúna (65.63%), Muniz Freire (65.00%), and Ibitirama (56.00%). Only in the municipality of Guaçuí soils with low P content predominated (50%), and high P content was found in 35% of the samples (Table 8).

3.5.2 Phosphorus in medium-textured soils

In the samples from medium-textured soils from the municipalities of Irupi (84.85%), Ibatiba (77.78%), Iúna (75.38%), Guaçuí (62.69%), and Ibitirama (60.00%), high contents of P were observed. Only in the municipality of Muniz Freire did soils with low P content predominate (43.86%), and high P content was found in 1/3 of the samples (Table 9).

Table 8: Statistical measurements of phosphorus in clay soils for the municipalities of Guaçuí, Ibatiba, Ibitirama, Irupi, Iúna, and Muniz Freire

Statistical measurement	Municipalitie					
	Guaçuí	Ibatiba	Ibitirama	Irupi	Iúna	Muniz freire
Medium content mg dm ⁻³	14.08	37.97	32.22	46.61	33.29	21.85
Maximum content mg dm ⁻³	55.50	219.00	245.80	151.50	184.30	53.40
Minimum content mg dm ⁻³	1.90	3.00	3.40	11.30	3.00	4.00
CV (%)	110.95	129.88	159.09	96.08	118.87	79.82
Frequency (%) high content	35.00	88.89	56.00	100.00	65.63	65.00
Frequency (%) low content	50.00	5.56	12.00	0.00	15.63	5.00
Frequency (%) Medium content	15.00	5.56	32.00	0.00	18.75	30.00

Table 9: Statistical measurements of phosphorus in medium-textured soils for the municipalities of Guaçuí, Ibatiba, Ibitirama, Irupi, Iúna, and Muniz Freire

Statistical measurement	Municipalitie					
	Guaçuí	Ibatiba	Ibitirama	Irupi	Iúna	Muniz freire
Medium content mg dm ⁻³	55.97	88.50	59.45	82.70	83.23	28.39
Maximum content mg dm ⁻³	606.40	388.50	298.70	367.60	343.50	183.70
Minimum content mg dm ⁻³	3.50	2.70	2.30	5.30	4.60	1.30
CV (%)	157.96	88.11	103.13	98.94	92.22	132.18
Frequency (%) high content	62.69	77.78	60.00	84.85	75.38	33.33
Frequency (%) low content	22.39	7.41	25.00	4.55	4.62	43.86
Frequency (%) Medium content	14.93	14.81	15.00	10.61	20.00	22.81

The combined observation of data from all samples from the Caparaó Capixaba region showed that P contents in clayey soils ranged from 1.90 to 245.80 mg dm⁻³, with an average of 29.78 mg dm⁻³, and high P contents were the most frequent (64.52%), followed by medium (19.35%) and low (16.13%) contents. In medium-textured soils, P contents ranged from 1.30 to 606.40 mg dm⁻³, with an average of 68.11 mg dm⁻³. High P contents were the most frequent (66.92%), followed by low (16.92%) and medium (16.16%) contents (Table 4).

Medium to high P frequency ranges were the most frequently found in the soils studied in the Caparaó Capixaba region. However, this result differs from those found by other authors who studied soils under natural conditions, unaltered by anthropogenic activities in Espírito Santo, where low contents of P in the soil were observed (PIRES *et al.*, 2003; GROTH *et al.*, 2013). Several authors consider P to be limiting for plant development even in soils with good fertility (BRASIL *et al.*, 2020; DE SISTO; MACDOUGALL, 2024). Other authors, due to P fixation, a characteristic of tropical soils, in addition to the low contents in soils without anthropogenic alteration, consider the supply of this element necessary, which represents one

of the main limitations to the adequate development of plants and crop production (DADALTO; FULLIN, 2001; HEMIELEVSKI *et al.*, 2025).

The higher P contents found in the soils of this study can be explained by the common use in this region of fertilizers with reactive and non-reactive natural phosphate and the Mehlich 1 extraction method (OLIVEIRA *et al.*, 2015). The use of different P sources for fertilization implies the use of versatile extractants that accurately estimate the available P in the soil, or that can correlate with plant absorption. The Mehlich 1 method, which acts on the soil by acid dissolution, consists of solubilizing the forms of P bound to Ca, Al, and Fe in descending order of effectiveness; thus, it has the disadvantage, due to the preferential extraction of Ca compounds, of overestimating the available contents in soils with the presence of Ca phosphates as a primary mineral (MEHLICH, 1978). Also, in those soils that received fertilization with natural phosphates (GATIBONI *et al.*, 2003; BORTOLON *et al.*, 2011; OLIVEIRA *et al.*, 2015).

Due to problems with overestimating P in soils with added natural phosphates, Mehlich (1984) proposed modifications to the method, creating the Mehlich 3 method, taking into account the advantage of the simultaneous extraction of other macronutrients and micronutrients. To avoid problems of overestimating P availability, methods sensitive only to the forms of P accessible to plants can be used. Proposed by Amer *et al.* (1955), the Anion Exchange Resin (AER) in sheets or spheres has permanent anion adsorption sites. A favorable characteristic of the method is that it can also be used in alkaline soil, not overestimating P availability in soils that have received natural phosphate (SILVA; RAIJ, 1999).

As can be seen in the dendrogram (Figure 2), three similar groups were formed with respect to the variables studied (Ca, Mg, K, S, and P), the first was formed by the cities of Ibitirama, Irupí, and Iúna. The second is by Guaçuí and Muniz Freire, and finally, the third is by Ibatiba.

Figure 2: Grouping of the studied municipalities obtained based on the variables studied.

Based on the maximum and minimum contents and the coefficients of variation shown in Tables 3 to 9, the contents of the studied nutrients indicated variability within the municipalities.

4 CONCLUSIONS

Based on the results of the chemical analyses of the sampled soils, the following conclusions were reached:

Soils of the Caparaó Capixaba region are deficient in calcium and magnesium.

Potassium and sulphur were found in high contents in the soils of all sampled municipalities.

High contents of phosphorus were found in the soils of the municipalities of Caparaó Capixaba region.

5. FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

Due to the low contents of Ca and Mg observed in the soils of the Caparaó Capixaba region, applications of Ca and Mg carbonates or Ca and Mg oxides, with high contents of these elements, are necessary.

Regarding the high contents of K and S, differentiated treatments will be necessary to avoid toxicity or nutritional imbalance, with correct soil analysis, nutritional monitoring of coffee plants with annual foliar analysis, and selection of the correct source for the application of these or other nutrients, since many fertilizers mainly contain S in high concentrations that are often not accounted for in technical recommendations.

The high contents of phosphorus found in the soils of the municipalities of Caparaó Capixaba region may be linked to the analysis method and source, where phosphorus is being overestimated. It would be important to include P-resin in routine analyses and to conduct new research to validate P-resin interpretation tables for the soils of the state of Espírito Santo, increasing the reliability of analytical results.

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